

School Nurse-Led Intervention for Health-Related Chronic Absenteeism

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Background

- School absenteeism leads to poor performance in school, has negative social effects, reduced adult health & socioeconomic outcomes
- Chronic absenteeism is missing 10% of the school year or greater than two days per month
- School nurses use education and expertise to recognize and intervene in health-related problems including identification of students who are at risk for chronic absenteeism.

Problem

School nurses are:

- Under utilized in their area of expertise
- Accessible to children and families and play crucial role in decreasing absenteeism
- Well positioned to address SDOH especially education
- Reduce the potential for dropping out of high school

Purpose

The purpose of this project is to develop and implement a process to

- Identify students who have health-related chronic absences
- Notify school nurse of students who have health-related chronic absences for follow-up using the NASN School Nurse-Led Active Surveillance Manual
- Document and evaluate effectiveness of school nurse intervention

References

Framework

Results

22-23 STUDENTS WITH CLUSTER HEALTH-RELATED ABSENCES

- Students with COVID
- Students Marked Other
- Students Eligible For Referral
- Students Marked Illness
- Students Not Eligible For Referral
- Students Referred

Outreach Actions

Method

Setting: Southern California school district high school with ~1800 students
Participants: Principal, Attendance clerk, Health clerk, District data specialist, Assistant Superintendent Ed Services, School nurse
Operational Definition: Cluster health-related absences = missing four or more consecutive days due to an illness related absence
Measures: Baseline data from 19-20 for cluster health-related absences compare to 22-23; identification and accuracy in recording of cluster health-related absences referrals to school nurse; outreach to families

Recommendations

Districtwide Implementation of Health-Related Tracking Procedure:

- Initial and Ongoing training for Attendance Clerk, Health Clerk and School Nurse
- Develop and Implement standardized triage tool to be used by unlicensed assistive staff to help determine urgency of follow-up
- Modify email sent by attendance clerk to include school nurse contact information and availability for students with cluster health-related absences

Improved Outreach & Case Management

- Implement consistent case management and utilize case management tracking tool

Ongoing Evaluation

- Consistency of documentation and referral procedure
- Measure effectiveness of nurse intervention

Implications

School nurse involvement in attendance leads to:

- Students returning to school quicker
- Case management = increased attendance
- Increased attendance = academic success
- Increased workload for school nurses due to increased referral of absent students